

Efficiency of biosorbents in the removal of emerging contaminants from real wastewater

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Wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) face some limitations regarding the removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) allowing them to enter surface and ground waters degrading their quality, thus hindering water reuse and drinking water production [1]. Namely, traditional technologies are not efficient in the removal of these kinds of pollutants, so the WWTPs need an upgrade with new, advanced technologies. One of the most promising methods is adsorption on activated carbon (AC) but it has its limitations, mostly regarding the price of the adsorbent [1, 2]. To overcome these limitations, a wide range of materials of low-cost biological origin (biosorbents) were investigated as potential alternatives to AC [2]. The literature mostly provides information on the adsorption of CECs from single- or multiple-component solutions which are important for understanding the process but not for the removal efficiency for the application under real conditions. Wastewater is a much more complex matrix and the adsorption is influenced by more factors. For that reason, the adsorption tests in real wastewater are essential for the evaluation of a material for its application as an adsorbent.

In this study, six biosorbents were tested for the CEC removal from a municipal WWTP biological effluent: wood-based hydrochar, two types of kraft lignin of different origins, agricultural waste-based biochar, and its chemically modified forms. Hydrochar was obtained from wood processing waste by hydrothermal carbonization. Lignins were isolated from thistle and pinecone by the kraft process. Biochar was produced by slow pyrolysis of raspberry pruning residues and activated by K_2CO_3 and $ZnCl_2$. Batch adsorption tests were conducted by mixing 0.1 g of each biosorbent with 100 ml of WWTP effluent at the original pH for 24 h. Afterward, the mixture was filtrated through 0.45 μm pore-size membranes. UHPLC–MS/MS was used to determine the initial and residual CEC concentrations.

The results showed that furosemide and ofloxacin were completely removed by hydrochar, while carbamazepine and diclofenac acid were less efficiently removed (60% and 71%, respectively). Hydrochlorothiazide (HCTZ) and sotalol concentrations were twice as low after adsorption but losartan was poorly removed. Diclofenac acid, furosemide, losartan, and ofloxacin were removed completely by both types of lignin. Pinecone lignin was slightly more efficient in the removal of carbamazepine and sotalol. The results suggest that kraft lignin is a promising material for CEC removal from real wastewater, regardless of its origin. $ZnCl_2$ -activated biochar turned out to be the most efficient in CEC removal. All components were completely removed except diclofenac acid and diltiazem, with the latter being removed poorly by all biosorbents.

Acknowledgments

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EU executive agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This study is conducted under the project TwiNSol-CECs that has received funding from Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement no.101059867.

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